

The Role of IL-6, Vitamin D Deficiency and TSH on Chronic Tonsillitis Children: A Clinical Study

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Abstract

Background. It is very normal for kids to get tonsillitis. Tonsillectomy is the most common surgery done on kids who get tonsils over and over again. When a child is three to ten years old, their tonsils are at their most immune-boosting. Because of this, the tonsils stand out more during this time and eventually show age-dependent involution. **Aims of the study.** Evaluating the role of vitamin D, interleukin 6, and thyroid-stimulating hormone in tonsillitis and the relationship of these biomarkers in controlling the severity of the disease in children. **Methodology.** A case-control study was conducted including 30 children with chronic pharyngitis with an average age of 14.19 years, as well as a control group of 25 healthy children. The study took place at the Al-Kadhimiya Teaching Hospital from 10/2/2022 to 10/8/2023, after approval by the Research Committee of the College of Medicine at Al-Nahrain University and obtaining verbal consent from the parents. Blood samples were collected and the necessary analyzes were performed. CRP, ASO, and interleukin-6 levels were measured using an ELISA. The total number of white blood cells was calculated using a Sysmex CBC device, and the ESR was measured with a Fast ESR device. TSH and vitamin D levels were analyzed using a Cobas E411 device. **Result.** The levels of several biochemical and immune markers were very different between the patient group and the control group ($P < 0.001$). In the patient group, levels of ASOT, CRP, ESR, WBC, TSH, and IL-6 all went up, while levels of vitamin D went down. The results also showed that TSH and IL-6 levels were different in men and women with chronic tonsillitis. However, there were no statistically significant changes in the other indicators ($P > 0.05$). **Conclusions.** The results indicate that there are significant differences in biochemical and immunological indicators between children with chronic tonsillitis and healthy children. This can be explained by the increased inflammatory response in patients, which raises ASOT, CRP, ESR, and IL-6 levels and lowers vitamin D levels.

Introduction

Tonsillitis is the medical term used to describe the inflammation or infection of the tonsils, which are located in the back of the throat. Some other parts of the back of the throat, like the adenoids and the lingual tonsils, could get swollen too. People with acute tonsillitis get sick with their tonsils because of different

types of bacteria or viruses. It is also possible for peritonsillar tumors to form. Some people get tonsillitis that won't go away, which is known as chronic tonsillitis. This can cause tonsil stones. It is called recurring tonsillitis when someone gets it more than once a year. If someone has chronic or repeated tonsillitis, their tonsils get swollen over and over again.

More Information

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This can really lower their quality of life [1,2]. Children often get tonsillitis, but kids younger than 2 years old don't get it very often. Staphylococcus bacteria are more likely to cause tonsillitis in kids 5 to 15 years old. Viruses are more likely to cause tonsillitis in kids younger than 5 years old. A lot of research has shown that 15.9% of school-aged kids carry the group A Streptococcus virus [3,4]. Many kids get sore throats and tonsils so often that they think it's just part of being a kid. A study found that about 30% of people with peritonsillar sores need to have their tonsils taken out. Another study found that tonsillitis comes back in 11.7% of Norwegian children and 12.1% of Turkish children [5]. A lot of these people are given antibiotics, which help for a little while but then the tonsillitis comes back. Researchers at Washington University School of Medicine found that biofilms made by germs in the tonsils' warm and wet folds make illnesses that keep coming back worse [6]. A study that used a new imaging method on single pieces of human nasal tissue found biofilms in 70.8% of people with chronic tonsillitis. Biofilms were found on the surface cells of many patients who were waiting for an adenotonsillectomy because they had chronic tonsillitis and adenoiditis. Biofilms like these are also found in illnesses of the nose, ears, and throat, such as chronic rhinosinusitis and chronic otitis media with effusion [7,8]. On a histological study, the crypt epithelium is still there, but it is sometimes thinned out and damaged, and there are areas of ceratinization. On the subepithelial plane, there were a lot of small lymph nodes, but the germinative centers and mantle zone were easy to see. From the outside, you can see fibrosis, and inside the tonsillar crypt, you can find cell waste. Lots of people get two main kinds of chronic tonsillitis. Each has a different number of lymph nodes and a range of sizes for those nodes [9]. Antigen activation of T cells in the tonsil crypt epithelium has been shown to make Th1 cytokines (like IL-2) and Th2 cytokines (like IL-4, IL-5, IL-6, and IL-13). Th1 cytokines make inflammation worse, while Th2 cytokines make it better. Th1 type cytokines are made the most [10, 11]. When someone has tonsils, their body starts by making Th1-type cytokines, like IFN- γ and TNF- α . In the end, it makes cytokines of the Th2 type. The tissue has a lot of TNF- α , IL-1, and IL-6 because monocytes and macrophages are making too much of them because bacteria keep setting them off. The stress was the cause of the rise in IL-6 after 24 hours of culture. Cytokines do different things, but we know what they do [12,13]. Tests of the immune system in palatine tonsils have been used to learn a lot about the role of both local and general immunity. It seems that tonsils, even ones that are damaged, may still be able to keep the immune system healthy. The study's aims were to find out where the cells that make cytokines (TNF- α and IL-6)

are found in different types of tonsils from people with TH and RT, how much of these cytokines are made in TH and RT, and how much IFN- γ and IL-4 can be made by lymphocytes in the blood [14,15]. One more thing that has been linked to the condition is not getting enough sun in the winter, which makes it harder for the body to make vitamin D. Vitamin D is an important part of the immune system. It changes the functions of immune cells such as B and T lymphocytes in many ways. Due to the fact that it turns T helper cells into T helper 2 state [16], it is thought to have an impact on both immune systems. Vitamin D is also important for making antibacterial peptides (AMPs), such as β -defensin and cathelicidin, which are released when the immune system detects viruses or bacteria that are trying to infect the body. These peptides are the two main way that URT defends itself. These peptides directly stop the growth of microorganisms in tissues, showing a wide range of antimicrobial action. Vitamin D that is oil-soluble is made in the skin when it is exposed to sunlight and can also be found in food. It is also important for the formation of bones in the skeletal system [17,18].

Methodology

A case-control study that included 30 children with chronic pharyngitis. Their average age was 14.19 years, with a group of 25 healthy children. The study was conducted at the Al-Kadhimiya Teaching Hospital for the period from 10/2/2022 to 10/8/2023. The Research Committee at the College of Medicine, Al-Nahrain University, gave their ethical approval for the study to go ahead. The parents of the children gave their verbal permission before blood was drawn. All the information was written down based on the guidelines for inclusion criteria. A blood test was done within 30 minutes of each person giving 5 ml of blood and putting 2 ml of blood in an EDTA tube. Three milliliters of blood were put in a gel tube and left at room temperature for fifteen minutes until it coagulated. The blood was then split using a centrifuge set to 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. We separated the blood serum and put it at -20 degrees C⁰ until we were ready to use it. ELISA (enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay) was used to measure the amounts of CRP, ASO titer, and interleukin 6. A Sysmex CBC device was used to count the white blood cells, and a Fast ESR device was used to measure the ESR for 30 minutes. Cobas E411 was used to measure TSH and vitamin D levels.

Statistical Analysis

A lot of the time, statistical analysis is used to look at numbers. It also gives us ways to describe data and make easy assumptions about continuous and categorical data. The process includes gathering information that will be used to test the connection between two sets of statistical data. All the information in this study is shown as the mean with a standard

variation. The statistical studies were done with SPSS (version 26) and the dependent t-test (two-tailed) and the independent t-test (two-tailed) for variables with a normally distributed distribution. For variables with a non-normal distribution, the Mann-Whitney U test and the Wilcoxon test were used. $M < 0.05$ was seen as statistically significant.

Ethical Approval

Before the samples were taken, all of the patients who were going to be part of this study were properly informed and gave their verbal permission. The Committee on Publication Ethics at the College of Medicine, Al-Nahrain University, gave its approval to the study.

Results

Characteristics of children with chronic tonsillitis and the control group

A group of children with chronic tonsillitis ($n = 60$) was compared with a control group ($n = 25$) in terms of age and gender. In the study, the average age of the people in the control group was 12.92 ± 4.00 years, and the average age of the people in the sick group was 14.19 ± 5.66 years. There was no statistically significant difference in age between the two groups ($P > 0.05$). There were 12 men and 13 women in the control group, 30 men and 30 women in the sick group, and there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups in terms of gender ($P > 0.05$).

Table 1: Comparison between the Characteristics of Children with Chronic Tonsillitis and the Control Group

Parameters		Control group (n=25) Mean $\pm$ SD	Patients group (n=60) Mean $\pm$ SD	P. value
Age		12.92 $\pm$ 4.00	14.19 $\pm$ 5.66	>0.05 ^{NS}
Sex	Male	12	30	>0.05 ^{NS}
	Female	13	30	

Characteristics of children with chronic tonsillitis

Figure 1: Comparison between the Characteristics of Children with Chronic Tonsillitis

Comparison of biochemical and immunological examination standards between children with chronic tonsillitis and the control group

The results showed that there were large, statistically significant differences between children with chronic tonsillitis and the control group in the levels of many biochemical and immunological indicators. This group's mean ASOT level was 100.00 ± 0.00 , while the patient group's was 338.89 ± 124.84 ($P < 0.001$). Also, the sick group had a mean CRP level of 11.57 ± 8.33 , while the control group had a mean CRP level of 3.94 ± 2.17 . The mean ESR for the control group was 16.12 ± 5.91 , while

it was 31.14 ± 7.80 for the sick group ($P < 0.001$). This group's WBC number was 7.11 ± 1.38 while the patient group's was 9.01 ± 1.60 ($P < 0.001$). The patient group had a TSH level of 2.62 ± 0.55 , while the control group's level was 1.39 ± 0.45 . This group had a mean vitamin D level of 28.88 ± 5.88 , while the sick group only had a mean level of 11.91 ± 4.00 ($P < 0.001$). Lastly, the sick group had an average IL-6 level of 29.39 ± 6.70 , while the control group had an average of 6.68 ± 1.63 . The data show that there are big differences in biochemical and immune system factors between the kids who had chronic tonsillitis and the kids who were not sick.

Table 2: Differences in Levels of ASOT, CRP, ESR, WBC, TSH, Vitamin D, and IL-6 between Children with Chronic Tonsillitis and Control Groups

Parameters	Control group (n=25) Mean ± SD	Patients group (n=60) Mean ± SD	P. value
ASOT	100.00 ± 0.00	338.89 ± 124.84	<0.001
CRP	3.94 ± 2.17	11.57 ± 8.33	<0.001
ESR	16.12 ± 5.91	31.14 ± 7.80	<0.001
WBC	7.11 ± 1.38	9.01 ± 1.60	<0.001
TSH	1.39 ± 0.45	2.62 ± 0.55	<0.001
Vitamin D	28.88 ± 5.88	11.91 ± 4.00	<0.001
IL-6	6.68 ± 1.63	29.39 ± 6.70	<0.001

DIFFERENCES IN LEVELS OF ASOT, CRP, ESR, WBC, TSH, VIT.D, AND IL-6 BETWEEN CHILDREN WITH CHRONIC TONSILLITIS AND CONTROL GROUPS

Figure 2: levels of ASOT, CRP, ESR, WBC, TSH, Vitamin D and IL-6 among Study Group

Comparison of biochemical and immunological examination standards between males and females with chronic tonsillitis

The results showed slight differences in some biochemical and immunological parameters between males and females with chronic tonsillitis. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups ($P > 0.05$). The mean ASOT level was 352.38 ± 124.97 for men and 320.00 ± 126.49 for women. The average CRP level in men was 11.00 ± 7.80 , while it was 12.55 ± 9.50 in women. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups ($P > 0.05$). The mean ESR for men was 29.90 ± 8.79 and for women it was 32.87 ± 6.02 , and there was no statistically significant difference ($P > 0.05$). The WBC number was 8.99 ± 1.67

in men and 9.05 ± 1.55 in women, but the difference wasn't statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). The average TSH level in men was 2.83 ± 0.47 , while it was 2.32 ± 0.52 in women. This difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). Men had an average vitamin D level of 11.82 ± 4.07 , while women had an average of 12.05 ± 4.03 , and the difference was not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). In the end, the average amount of IL-6 in men was 31.22 ± 6.53 , while it was 26.82 ± 6.26 in women. This difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). The data show that TSH and IL-6 levels are different in men and women with chronic tonsillitis. However, there were no statistically significant differences in the other parameters.

Table 3: Differences in ASOT, CRP, ESR, WBC, TSH, Vitamin D, and IL-6 Levels between Males and Females with Chronic Tonsillitis

Parameters	Male group (n=30) Mean ± SD	Female group (n=30) Mean ± SD	P. value
ASOT	352.38 ± 124.97	320.00 ± 126.49	>0.05
CRP	11.00 ± 7.80	12.55 ± 9.50	>0.05
ESR	29.90 ± 8.79	32.87 ± 6.02	>0.05
WBC	8.99 ± 1.67	9.05 ± 1.55	>0.05
TSH	2.83 ± 0.47	2.32 ± 0.52	<0.05
Vitamin D	11.82 ± 4.07	12.05 ± 4.03	>0.05
IL-6	31.22 ± 6.53	26.82 ± 6.26	<0.05

Differences in ASOT, CRP, ESR, WBC, TSH, Vit.D, and IL-6 levels between males and females with chronic tonsillitis

Figure 3: The levels of ASOT, CRP, ESR, WBC, TSH, Vitamin D, and IL-6 Levels in Males and Females with Chronic Tonsillitis

Analysis of the correlation between biochemical and immunological examination indicators in children with chronic tonsillitis

We looked at the Pearson correlation values between biochemical and immunological exam signs in kids with chronic tonsillitis. Age and ASOT level were found to have a negative association that was not statistically significant ($r = -0.320, P = 0.103$). There was also a positive link between the CRP level and both age ($r = 0.269, P = 0.227$) and ASOT ($r = 0.299, P = 0.108$), but these connections were not statistically important. If you look at the other hand, there was a strong link between ASOT level and ESR ($r = 0.467, P = 0.004$).

There were also no statistically significant links between WBC and any of the other measures. For example, the correlation coefficient between WBC and ASOT was 0.314, $P = 0.066$; the correlation coefficient

between WBC and CRP was 0.215, $P = 0.262$; and the correlation coefficient between WBC and ESR was 0.145, $P = 0.407$. There were no statistically significant links between the TSH level and other markers, such as ASOT ($r = -0.007, P = 0.968$) or CRP ($r = -0.021, P = 0.914$). Regarding vitamin D level, the results did not show statistically significant correlations with other indicators. Finally, the results showed that there was a statistically non-significant positive correlation between IL-6 level and Vitamin D ($r = 0.229, P = 0.178$), while there were no statistically significant correlations between IL-6 and other indicators. These results indicate the existence of some relationships between biochemical and immunological examination indicators, but most of them were not statistically significant except for the relationship between ASOT and ESR.

Table 4: Pearson correlation coefficients between indicators of different examinations

Parameters		Age	ASOT	CRP	ESR	WBC	TSH	Vit.D
ASOT	Pearson Correlation	-.320						
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.103						
CRP	Pearson Correlation	.269	.299					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.227	.108					
ESR	Pearson Correlation	-.185	.467**	.160				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.356	.004	.398				
WBC	Pearson Correlation	-.087	.314	.215	.145			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.671	.066	.262	.407			
TSH	Pearson Correlation	-.307	-.007	-.021	-.221	-.117		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.120	.968	.914	.195	.505		
Vit.D	Pearson Correlation	-.194	.049	-.090	.190	-.183	.077	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.333	.776	.637	.267	.293	.655	
IL-6	Pearson Correlation	-.106	-.037	-.252	.076	.112	.008	.229
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.598	.828	.179	.658	.523	.962	.178

Pearson correlation coefficients between indicators of different examinations

Figure 4: Pearson Correlation Coefficients between Indicators

Discussion

A weaker immune system may be linked to not getting enough vitamin D, especially when it comes to keeping tonsillitis from coming back. Researchers have found that vitamin D has a big impact on the immune system. It changes both natural and learned immunity and reduces inflammation [19]. Two antibacterial peptides, cathelicidin and beta-defensin, are made more when vitamin D is present. Having these all over the body is a big part of our natural defense because they kill germs and toxins. Because of this, vitamin D may help protect against getting tonsillitis over and over again by stopping the growth of biofilm made of bacteria [20,21]. There were only three papers that were good enough for this study. Each of these three articles looked at kids who had chronic or recurrent tonsillitis and kids who did not have chronic or recurrent tonsillitis. In the research that was done to find out the risk of chronic tonsillitis, different vitamin D values were used as cut-off points, Yildiz et al. [22], a lack of vitamin D (<50nmol/L) was used to show a higher chance of getting tonsillitis again. The work of Collak et al. People who don't get enough vitamin D (20–32ng/mL, or 50–80nmol/L) or too little vitamin D (< 20ng/mL, or < 50 nmol/L) are more likely to get chronic tonsillitis. Until then, Aydin et al. [24], vitamin D levels were stopped at less than 80 nmol/L, which means the person did not have enough vitamin D. People who didn't get enough vitamin D were more likely to get chronic tonsillitis, according to all three studies. But only Aydin et al. had a result that was statistically important, with an OR of 32.4 (1.9–551.4). The amount of harm that needs to happen (NNH) that Aydin et al. [24], is two, which means two kids did not get enough vitamin D and one kid had tonsillitis over and over again. Something that isn't good is that the sunshine changes all the time. It was tried by the studies that they did their work at times when climate change would be less noticeable, so the data might not be fully useful in Indonesia. The weather in Indonesia is warm and close to the equator, so people there get more sunlight all year than people who live farther away. Even though the studies were done in subtropical areas, it seems possible that the number of vitamin-D deficient people would be different in each area because of the amount of sunlight they get. Soesanti et al., on the other hand, said that 15% of healthy children in Indonesia did not have enough vitamin D and 90.8% did not have enough vitamin D. In the same way, Collak et al. [23], it was found that 90.6% of the children in the control group (Turkey children without severe tonsillitis) did not have enough vitamin D. At the same time, more people in the control group (33.8%) were not getting enough vitamin D than in the group of healthy Indonesian children. Aydin et al. and Yildiz et al,

on the other hand, found that none of the children in the control group (Istanbul children without chronic tonsillitis and/or tonsillopharyngitis) did not have enough vitamin D or vitamin D [25,26]. This study showed that vitamin D might help people who get tonsillitis over and over again. In the group that got vitamin D, the tonsillar sections went back to the way they were before they were treated. If you get enough vitamin D, your antibodies will work better. There are many ways that vitamin D can change immune cells, such as dendritic cells, B lymphocytes, T lymphocytes, and NK cells [22], VDRs are found on T cells, B cells, antigen-presenting cells, macrophages, and dendritic cells, among other cells. Vitamin D6 can change both the natural and adaptive immune systems. Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) like defensin β and cathelicidin are made more when vitamin D is present. These AMPs are a natural way for the body to protect itself. Of these, all of them naturally keep germs that could be painful away. People who get tonsillitis usually have less of the AMPs cathelicidin and defensin b2 on the tonsil surface and in the tonsillar crypt epithelium than healthy people [27]. People who get tonsillitis over and over again have been found to have low amounts of AMP4. Because it lowers the production of cytokines that cause inflammation and boosts the growth of induced regulatory T cells, vitamin D stops active lymphocytes from growing. A lot of research has shown that getting enough vitamin D can help keep you from getting acute respiratory illnesses [28]. This was especially true for people who didn't get enough vitamin D. There are a lot of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the lymphoid tissue and saliva of kids who get tonsils over and over again¹⁸. In particular, kids who have chronic tonsillitis have more TNF- α , IL-1, and IL-6 in their saliva. However, only the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-6 showed changes that were statistically important [29]. In our work, IL-6 levels were also much higher in rat tonsil tissue compared to PTA tonsil tissue and tonsil tissue that wasn't inflamed. But it was interesting that tonsillar T cells never made nearly as much IL-6 as peripheral T cells did, no matter what the situation was. It's important to note that this only happened with IL-6; other cytokines were released at similar levels by cells from the tonsils and blood. We found that tonsillar T cells have a skewed TCR response and low IL-6 release. This suggests that IL-6 may not be a very important cytokine in the tonsillar immune response [30,31]. Given that TSH can be made by leukocytes, it seems likely that TSH may function in the immune system as a cytokine-like mediator. This is supported by studies showing that TSHR is expressed on lymphoid and myeloid cells, and it can also be inferred from studies showing that TSH can change the way lymphocytes work. It has been shown that TSH can

increase antibody responses in in vitro plaque tests and boost the growth of lymphocytes when concanavalin-A and phytohemagglutinin are present [31,32]. When combined with interleukin (IL)-2, TSH can also help natural killer cells do their job. When TSH is applied to splenic DCs, the phagocytic response gets stronger in the lab, and IL-1 β and IL-12 levels rise when phagocytic triggers are present. Some lymphocyte, monocyte, and granulocyte precursors in the bone marrow show the TSHR, but not all of them do. When TSH is used to stimulate bone marrow cells, the CD11b⁻ population releases more TNF α . Bone marrow cells that are stimulated by TSH have a standard cAMP response and the Jak2 kinase is quickly phosphorylated. These studies used in vitro systems, which meant they weren't as affected by other things TSH might do in living things. This means it's likely that they showed direct TSH activity on TSHR⁺ immune cells [33,34]. TSH, on the other hand, might have a secondary effect on the immune system by changing the amount of T3 and T4 in the thyroid. Then, this would alter the function or development of cells in the bone marrow and/or secondary lymphoid organs. This is true, as shown by studies that show the immune system works less well when there are low amounts of thyroid hormones in the blood. In the TSHR faulty C.RF-hyt/hyt mouse, which can't use TSH and is therefore very hypothyroid, the bone marrow doesn't make as many B cells [35,36]. Mice that were hyt/hyt for C.RF had more and more pro-B cells in the cell cycle after being given T4. Also, the bone marrow, thymus, and liver of mice that did not have genes for the T3 receptors α 1 and α 2 had a lot fewer cells. Any kind of white blood cell in the spleen did this, like B cells, T cells, granulocytes, and macrophages. These researches show that TSH and thyroid hormone have many different effects on the defense systems, both in the body's center and its edges [37].

Conclusion

The results indicate that there are significant differences in biochemical and immunological indicators between children with chronic tonsillitis and healthy children. These differences may be explained by the increased inflammatory response in patients. This response results in elevated levels of ASOT, CRP, ESR, and IL-6, which are indicators of active inflammation in the body. In addition, patients notice a decrease in vitamin D levels, which is a vitamin that plays an important role in regulating the immune system and reducing inflammation. This decrease may be due to the body's increased consumption of vitamin D during a chronic inflammatory response or the result of poor absorption. These findings reflect the effects of chronic inflammation on the general health status of children with chronic tonsillitis.

References

- [1] American Academy of Otolaryngology Tonsillitis. 2018. [Accessed January 6, 2018]. Available from: <http://www.entnet.org/content/tonsillitis>.
- [2] Hayes K. Chronic and recurrent tonsillitis: what to know. 2017. [Accessed January 6, 2018]. Available from: <https://www.verywell.com/chronic-and-recurrent-tonsillitis-1191984>. [
- [3] Shah UK. Tonsillitis and peritonsillar abscess. *Drugs & Diseases. Otolaryngology and Facial Plastic Surgery*. Medscape; [Accessed January 6, 2018].
- [4] Wald ER. Commentary: antibiotic treatment of pharyngitis. *Pediatr Rev*. 2001;22(8):255–256.
- [5] Kvestad E, Kvaerner KJ, Roysamb E, Tambs K, Harris JR, Magnus P. Heritability of recurrent tonsillitis. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2005;131(5):383–387. doi: 10.1001/archotol.131.5.383
- [6] Ward D. Bacterial biofilms may be source of recurrent tonsillitis *Medicine & Health*. Washington University in St. Louis; 2018. [Accessed January 6, 2018].
- [7] Kania RE, Lamers GE, Vonk MJ, et al. Demonstration of bacterial cells and glycocalyx in biofilms on human tonsils. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2007;133(2):115–121. doi: 10.1001/archotol.133.2.115
- [8] Al-Mazrou KA, Al-Khattaf AS. Adherent biofilms in adenotonsillar diseases in children. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2008;134(1):20–23. doi: 10.1001/archoto.2007.18
- [9] Avramović V, Savić V, Stanković M. Scanning electron microscopic characteristics of human tonsillar crypt epithelium. *Acta Medica Medianae*. 1996a;1:19–28. doi: 10.1002/path.1711300205
- [10] Zhang PC, Pang YT, Loh KS, Wang DY. Comparison of histology between recurrent tonsillitis and tonsillar hipertrophy. *Clin Otolaryngol*. 2003;28:235–240. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2273.2003.00697.x
- [11] Passali D, Damiani V, Passáli GC, Passáli FM, Boccay A, Bellussi L. Structural and immunological characteristics of chronically inflamed adenotonsillar tissue in chidhood. *Clin Diagn Lab Immunol*. 2004;11(6):1154–1157. doi: 10.1128/CDLI.11.6.1154-1157.2004
- [12] Komorowska A, Komorowski J, Banasik M, Lewkowicz P, Tchórze-wski H. Cytokines locally produced by lymphocytes removed from the hypertrophic nasopharyngeal and palatine tonsils. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol*. 2005;69(7):937–941. doi: 10.1016/j.ijporl.2005.01.035
- [13] Kim J, Bhattacharjee R, Dayyat E, Snow AB, Kheirandish-Goza L, Goldman JL, et al. Increased cellular proliferation and inflammatory cytokines in tonsils derived from children with obstructive sleep

- apnea. *Pediatr Res.* 2009;66(4):423–428. doi: 10.1203/PDR.0b013e3181b453e3
- [14] Janeway CA, Jr How the immune system protects the host from infection. *Microbes Infect.* 2001;13(3):1167–1171. doi: 10.1016/s1286-4579(01)01477-0
- [15] Ma CS, Suryani S, Avery DT, Chan A, Nanan R, Santner-Nanan B, et al. Early commitment of naive human CD4+ T cells to the T follicular helper (Tfh) cell lineage is induced by IL-12. *Immunol Cell Biol.* 2009;87(8):590–600. doi: 10.1038/icb.2009.64
- [16] Relationship between serum vitamin D levels and childhood recurrent tonsillitis. *Elbistanlı MS, Güneş S, Yegin Y, Çelik M, Koçak H, Evren C, Kayhan F. Otolaryngol Open J.* 2017;3:16–21. doi: 10.17140/OTLOJ-3-135
- [17] Vitamin D for prevention of respiratory tract infections: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Charan J, Goyal JP, Saxena D, Yadav P. J Pharmacol Pharmacother.* 2012;3:300–303.
- [18] The association between vitamin D deficiency and recurrent tonsillitis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Mirza AA, Alharbi AA, Marzouki H, Al-Khatib T, Zawawi F. Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2020;163:883–891.
- [19] Di Rosa M, Malaguarnera M, Nicoletti F, Malaguarnera L. Vitamin D3: A helpful immuno-modulator. *Immunology.* 2011.
- [20] Ganz T. Defensins: Antimicrobial peptides of innate immunity. *Nature Reviews Immunology.* 2003.
- [21] Esposito S, Lelii M. Vitamin D and respiratory tract infections in childhood. *BMC Infectious Diseases.* 2015.
- [22] Yildiz I, Unuvar E, Zeybek U, Toptas B, Cacina C, Toprak S, et al. The role of vitamin D in children with recurrent Tonsillopharyngitis. *Ital J Pediatr.* 2012;
- [23] Collak A. Serum vitamin D levels in children with recurrent tonsillopharyngitis. *North Clin Istanbul.* 2014;
- [24] Aydin S, Aslan I, Yildiz I, Ağaçhan B, Toptaş B, Toprak S, et al. Vitamin D levels in children with recurrent tonsillitis. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol.* 2011;
- [25] Esposito S, Lelii M. Vitamin D and respiratory tract infections in childhood. *BMC Infectious Diseases.* 2015.
- [26] Soesanti F, Pulungan A, Tridjaja B, Batubara JR. Vitamin D profile in healthy children aged 7-12 years old in Indonesia. *Int J Pediatr Endocrinol [Internet].*
- [27] Wang TT, Nestel FP, Bourdeau V, Nagai Y, Wang Q, Liao J, et al. Cutting edge: 1,25-dihydroxy vitamin D3 is a direct inducer of antimicrobial peptide gene expression. *J. Immunol.* 2004;173(5):2909–2912.
- [28] Martineau AR, Jolliffe DA, Hooper RL, Greenberg L, Aloia JF, Bergman P, et al. Vitamin D supplementation to prevent acute respiratory tract infections: a systematic review and meta-analysis of individual participant data. *BMJ.* 2017;356:i6583.
- [29] Boiko NV, Stagnieva IV, Kim AS, Simbirtsev AS. Proinflammatory cytokine content in the saliva of children suffering from chronic tonsillitis. *Vestn. Otorinolaringol.* 2019;84:26–31. doi: 10.17116/otorino20198403126.
- [30] Cañete PF, Sweet RA, Gonzalez-Figueroa P, Papa I, Ohkura N, Bolton H, Roco JA, Cuenca M, Bassett KJ, Sayin I, Barry E, Lopez A, Canaday DH, Meyer-Hermann M, Doglioni C, de St Groth BF, Sakaguchi S, Cook MC, Vinuesa CG. Regulatory roles of IL-10-producing human follicular T cells. *J. Exp. Med.* 2019;216:1843–1856. doi: 10.1084/jem.20190493.
- [31] Coutelier JP, Kehrl JH, Bellur SS, Kohn LD, Notkins AL, Prabhakar BS. Binding and functional effects of thyroid stimulating hormone to human immune cells. *J Clin Immunol.* 1990;10:204–210.
- [32] Bagriacik EU, Klein JR. The thyrotropin (thyroid stimulating hormone) receptor is expressed on murine dendritic cells and on a subset of CD43RBhigh lymph node T cells: Functional role of thyroid stimulating hormone during immune activation. *J Immunol.* 2000;164:6158–6165.
- [33] Whetsell M, Bagriacik EU, Seetharamaiah GS, Prabhakar BS, Klein JR. Neuroendocrine-induced synthesis of bone marrow-derived cytokines with inflammatory immunomodulating properties. *Cell Immunol.* 1999;192:159–166.
- [34] Provinciali M, Di Stefano G, Fabris N. Improvement in the proliferative capacity and natural killer cell activity of murine spleen lymphocytes by thyrotropin. *Int J Immunopharmacol.* 1992;14:865–870.
- [35] Foster MP, Montecino-Rodriguez E, Dorshkind K. Proliferation of bone marrow pro-B cells is dependent on stimulation by the pituitary/thyroid axis. *J Immunol.* 1999;163:5883–5889.
- [36] Dorshkind K, Horseman ND. The roles of prolactin, growth hormone, insulin-like growth factor-I, and thyroid hormones in lymphocyte development and function: Insights from genetic models of hormone and hormone receptor deficiency. *Endocrine Rev.* 2005;21:292–312.
- [37] Aprin C, Philgren M, Fraichard A, Aubert D, Samarut J, Chassande O, Marvel J. Effects of T3Rα1 and T3Rα2 gene deletion on T and B lymphocyte development. *J Immunol.* 2000;164:152–160.